

FORMATION OF BORIDES AND OTHER PHASES
DURING WELDING OF BORON WITH ALUMINIUM

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The phase composition and structure of the interface in fibrous composites with aluminium matrix strengthened with boron fibres is studied. Methods of X-ray and electron diffraction were used to show that spinels $2Al_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3$ and $9Al_2O_3 \cdot 2B_2O_3$ are formed in the fiber-matrix interface in the solid-phase boron-aluminium combination process. AlB_{12} phase was found in the material produced under non-optimal conditions or following heat treatment. Liquid-phase combination of boron with aluminium results in the interface consisting of AlB_2 . However, it can be seen that the volume ratio of the fiber and the matrix, as well as the alloying elements in the matrix, affect the structure and phase composition of the boron-aluminium interface.

Physical and chemical interaction of heterogeneous materials results in the formation of a transition zone on the interface, most often, interlayers of a brittle phase. Various processes were elaborated in order to produce fibrous composites of the aluminium-boron system, therefore, it is most essential that the conditions for the formation of the fiber-matrix reaction products be investigated. The composite formation process is known to be controlled by the conditions for the physical contact, temperature and time of the process, as well as by the phase composition of the matrix and its state of aggregation. Besides, softening of the boron fibre was found to begin well before a complete layer of reaction products is formed when local interaction centres appear on its surface. In view of this, a challenging problem was posed - to study the phase composition of the transition zone in the aluminium-boron composite and the changes in the interface structure caused by changes in the state of aggregation of the matrix.

Boron fibres $0.14 \cdot 10^{-3}$ m in diameter, produced by gas-phase precipitation on a tungsten filament were used in our work. The boron layer had an "X-ray amorphous" structure. The fiber core phase composition was as follows: tungsten and tungsten borides W_2B_5 , WB_4 . Aluminium alloys: alloy I (99.5% Al, the rest are admixtures) and alloy II (aluminium-magnesium system alloy) were used as the composite matrix. Two methods were employed to produce the composite: pack rolling along the fibres of plasma semifinished products and impregnation of the solitary fibre or a cluster of fibres with liquid aluminium. To alter the state of the interface in the material produced by the solid-phase method it was heat treated in vacuo at 800 K over a period of $1.8 \cdot 10^2 - 3.6 \cdot 10^4$ sec. The phase composition of the interaction products

was investigated in the course of layer-by-layer dissolution of aluminium in a solution of chloric acid using the electron and X-ray diffraction methods for transilluminating the specimens through a thin aluminium layer. The fibre surface structure was studied with the help of an electron scanning microscope and a light microscope. To find out the kinetics of the interaction of the fibres and liquid aluminium the loss of fibre mass following the matrix dissolution was determined.

The composite rolling process is characterized by a short time of contact (about several seconds) of the fibre and matrix in the deformation centre and by intense power effect on the fibre. This latter fact facilitates the formation of active interaction centres on the fibre surface during rolling. However, the aluminium oxide film prevents the formation of bond centres in the solid-phase boron-aluminium composites. In spite of this, some authors obtained composites with good mechanical properties, particularly as regards the reinforcement. No signs of reaction could be seen on the fibre surface. In this connection, Metcalf /1/ put forward an assumption that in pseudofirst class composites (aluminium-boron, aluminium-steel) there exists an oxide bond between the aluminium oxide film and the natural oxide film on the fibre. However, the mechanism of this bond was not described.

Using the method of layer-wise dissolution of aluminium and in the course of subsequent investigation of the interface by electron diffraction spinels $2Al_2O_3 \cdot B_2O_3$ and $9Al_2O_3 \cdot 2B_2O_3$ could be identified in the composite after rolling. Similar composites were obtained by Kotieva et al. /2/ when they sintered the Al- Al_2O_3 mixture in the presence of the boron oxide. Judging by the phase diagram: aluminium oxide - boron oxide (Fig.1) an assumption can be made that at temperatures prevailing in the process aluminium oxide gets dissolved in the liquid boron oxide. Spinel seems to be formed when crystallization from the supersaturated solution occurs during cooling of the material. The AlB_{12} phase was identified in some points of the fibre surface. Its presence is due to the destruction of the aluminium oxide film in the process. No AlB_2 phase could be found in the material, obviously, because it got dissolved together with the matrix. During heat treatment of the material boride phases of aluminium grow in the points where the aluminium oxide film is damaged as a result of the interdiffusion of boron and aluminium. Due to growth defects the AlB_2 phase seems to be poorly bonded with the fibre surface and is removed together with the matrix when the surface is being prepared for investigations by electron diffraction. Lines corresponding to the AlB_2 phase were obtained during the Debye X-ray diffraction through a thin aluminium layer on the fibre surface. When alloy II was used the diffraction pattern on the interface of the material produced by the solid-phase method could not be interpreted. The only phase identified after heat treatment of the material was AlB_{12} . Similar results were obtained by Kim /3/ where the AlB_{12} phase only was found on the fiber-matrix interface following annealing.

Liquid-phase boron-aluminium contact displays strong influence of the volume ratios of the matrix and reinforcer as well as the alloying additives to the matrix on the phase formation process in the transition zone. X-raying of boron fibers through a thin aluminium layer after they had contacted the liquid matrix helped to identify the AlB_2 phase which is the nearest to the liquid solution of boron in aluminium on the phase diagram Al-B (Fig. 2). When the boron fiber contacts a large-volume melt intense dissolution of boron takes place. It is accompanied by strong and nonuniform reduction in the fibre diameter. In this case the AlB_2 grows due to crystallization from the supersaturated liquid solution, the diboride crystals having a rectilinear faceting /3/. When the melt volume is almost equal to that of the fibre aluminium gets saturated with boron quickly during the liquid-phase contact. In this case the phases on the interface grow both as a result of the interdiffusion of the components and following crystallization from the supersaturated solution. Both mechanisms of phase formation are closely interrelated, but at different temperatures their contributions are

Figure 1: Phase diagram aluminium oxide - boron oxide.

Figure 2: Phase diagram aluminium - boron.

A

B

Figure 3: Boron fiber surface after contact with the liquid alloy I.

Figure 4: Changes in the fiber mass after contact with liquid alloys I /2/ and II /1/ at 1000 K.

different too. In our case the AlB_2 phase always took the shape of rectangular crystals, therefore, the process of the phase growth on the alloy I-boron interface may be assumed to follow the second mechanism. When boron fibres interact with the liquid alloy II the processes occurring on the interface undergo great changes. Irrespective of the boron-aluminium volume ratio dissolution of boron is strongly inhibited and the fibre diameter is practically not changed. Fig. 4 shows changes in the fibre mass after contact with liquid alloys I and II at 1000 K. After the dissolution of alloy II a layer of fine (about $1.10^{-6}m$), faceted crystals was found on the fibre surface. They are a mixture of the AlB_2 , MgB_4 and AlB_{12} phases. The presence of magnesium in the melt and its surface activity seem to result in the levelling of the diffusion flows of boron and aluminium atoms near the interface. One of the authors of the work /4/ showed earlier that when the boron fibre contacts the Al-Mg system alloy magnesium segregates at the fiber surface. Therefore, when boron fibres contact the liquid melt II both the phase formation mechanisms mentioned above exist in the course of fiber-matrix interaction.

References

1. A.G. Metcalf and M.J. Klein. Interface in Fabricated Metal Matrix Composites.- J.of Adhesion, 1973,v.5, N1, p.57-72.
2. L.U. Kotieva, N.M. Ievleva, S.D. Shliapin et al. Tehnologiya poluchenia kompozitsionnogo materiala sistemy Al- Al_2O_3 - B_2O_3 .- Tsvetnaya metallurgiya, 1983, 5, p.25-28.
3. W. Kim, A. Koczak, A. Lowley. Interface reaction and characterization in B/Al composites.-ICCM/2. Proceed.of Inter. Conf. of Comp.Mater., Canada, 1978, p.487.
4. M.Kh. Shorshorov, V.I. Potapov, V.I. Antipov et al. O vzaimodeistvii bora so splavom sistemy aluminii - magnii. Fizika i khimiia obrabotki materialov, 1983, N3, p.142-143.

